

Informed Consent Form
Project “Evaluation of the Virtual Social Office application”

You are invited to participate in the research study called “Evaluation of the Virtual Social Office application”, by Melina Machado Miranda, from the National Council of Justice (CNJ) and researchers from the University of Brasília (UnB): the professors of the Department of Computer Science Prof. Rodrigo Bonifacio de Almeida, Prof. Edna Dias Canedo, Prof. Fernanda Lima, and the student Emille Catarine Rodrigues Cançado.

The objective of this research is to evaluate the quality of the Virtual Social Office application through interviews, questionnaires and usability evaluations, with former inmates from the Brazilian prison system, to identify their perception of the application, in their reintegration process into society. Therefore, I would like to consult you about your interest and availability to cooperate with the research.

You will receive all the necessary clarifications before, during and after the completion of the research, and we assure you that your name will not be disclosed, and the strictest confidentiality will be maintained through the total omission of information that allows you to be identified. Data arising from your participation in the research, such as questionnaires, interviews, voice recording and the use of the application, will be kept by the researchers responsible for the research.

Data collection will be carried out through interviews, questionnaires and usability assessments. It is for these procedures that you are being invited to participate. Your participation in the research involves minimal risks, such as some discomfort when answering questions. But no question is mandatory, so you can feel free to not answer something that makes you uncomfortable.

We ask for your permission to record your cell phone screen while interacting with the app and your voice during this contact. This recording will be used only by research participants and will not be published in any media. Your data is confidential and will not be revealed.

It is expected with this research to identify aspects considered important by former inmates in their social reintegration process and what information about services can be incorporated or improved in the Virtual Social Office application. The results will allow us to improve the quality of the services' information presented in the application.

Your participation is voluntary and without any remuneration or benefit. You are free to refuse to participate, withdraw your consent, or discontinue your participation at any time.

If you have any questions regarding the research, you can contact prof. Edna Dias Canedo by phone (xx)xxxxx-xxxx or by e-mail ednacanedo@unb.br.

The research team informs that the results of the study will be returned through improvements in the application, which can be published later in the scientific community. As we will not collect any information that identifies the participants, it will not be possible to provide results directly to individuals.

This project was reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Committee in Human and Social Sciences (CEP/CHS) of the University of Brasília. Information regarding this ICF signature or the rights of the research participant can be obtained through the e-mail: cep_chs@unb.br or by phone: (61) 3107 1592.

As interactions are being carried out virtually, due to the pandemic, your signature will be collected by recording your verbal acceptance. We recommend that you take a screenshot of the screen with this text, for any need.

I believe I have been sufficiently clarified about the information that I read or that was read to me, describing the study “Evaluation of the Virtual Social Office application”. I got in touch with prof. Edna Dias Canedo about my decision to participate in this study. It was clear to me what the purposes are, the procedures to be carried out, their discomforts and risks, and the guarantees of confidentiality. It was also clear that my participation is free of charge. I voluntarily agree to participate in this study and I may withdraw my consent at any time, before or during the same, without penalty or prejudice.

I agree to participate in the survey (state yes or no out loud).

Participant's signature

Signature: Edna Dias Canedo

Date: _____